

EMOTION REGULATION, DIFFICULTIES AND FRUSTRATION AMONG PRIVATE COLLEGE TEACHERS

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Emotion Regulation, Difficulties and Frustration among Private College Teachers

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Abstract

This study aims to measure emotion regulation, the challenges associated with it, and levels of frustration experienced by private college teachers. The primary objective was to measure these emotional dynamics and understand how they affect both personal well-being and professional effectiveness. Employing a quantitative correlational research design, the study utilized online surveys administered through Google Forms to collect data from a diverse sample of selected private college teachers. The demographic profile of the respondents revealed a broad range of ages and professional experiences, with a significant concentration in the 27-29 age bracket and a predominant representation of those with three to five years of teaching experience. This demographic diversity highlights the inclusion of both novice and veteran educators, offering a comprehensive view of emotion regulation and frustration within the teaching profession. The study's findings indicate that college teachers generally demonstrate high levels of emotional regulation, particularly in the areas of emotional integration and suppression. These findings suggest that teachers are adept at managing their emotions in ways that foster a constructive classroom environment and support their professional roles. Nevertheless, the study also identified notable difficulties in emotion regulation, such as instances of emotional dysregulation and challenges in managing emotional distress, which point to the need for specific interventions aimed at improving emotional resilience among educators. Furthermore, the study uncovered a significant level of frustration among college teachers, primarily linked to feelings of being undervalued or unappreciated in their professional roles. Despite their overall emotional resilience, these frustrations highlight the critical need for institutional measures that promote a culture of recognition and support, which could alleviate some of the professional dissatisfaction reported by the respondents. The study's results emphasize the necessity of developing targeted support mechanisms to address the identified difficulties in emotion regulation and to manage the sources of frustration experienced by college teachers. By promoting emotional awareness and offering practical emotion regulation strategies, educational institutions can enhance the well-being of teachers and improve job satisfaction. This approach not only benefits the educators themselves but also positively impacts the learning environment for students. Overall, the research underscores the importance of understanding and addressing the emotional experiences of selected private college teachers to foster a supportive and effective educational setting.

Keywords: *emotion regulation, difficulties, frustration, private college teachers*

Introduction

In the ever-evolving landscape of education, the role of teachers as emotional beings and their ability to effectively regulate their emotions have gained significant attention in recent years. The teaching profession is no longer seen as mere dissemination of knowledge but also an emotional endeavor. In fact, there is now a growing recognition that teachers' emotional well-being is intrinsically linked to their capacity to navigate the complex demands of their profession (Daniels & Buric, 2021), making it essential to understand the dynamics of emotion regulation, frustration and difficulties in emotion regulation.

Emotional regulation, as defined by McCrae and Gross (2020), is simply referred as attempts to influence emotion in ourselves or others. It involves recognizing, evaluating, and modifying emotional responses to adapt to varying situations and demands. Frustration, on the other hand, represents the emotional response to obstacles, setbacks, or unmet expectations (Hwang, 2022). The concepts of emotional regulation and frustration are indeed pertinent for teachers, as they are confronted with emotionally charged classrooms, diverse student needs, student behavior, administrative challenges, personal issues, among other potential sources of frustrations.

These concepts are present in the literature. Studies such as those by Donker et al. (2020) and Go et al. (2020), for instance, delve into the emotional challenges faced by teachers, including burnout, emotional exhaustion, and the use of emotion regulation strategies. Meanwhile, the work of Daniels and Buric (2021) emphasizes the need to move beyond simplistic views of teacher emotions and student outcomes, necessitating a more comprehensive understanding of emotion regulation and factors associated to it.

Looking closely into the Philippine context, emotion regulation amid frustrating experiences is an expected behavior among teachers given that the standards require them to possess not only technical and professional competence but also dignity, reputation, and high moral values. The expectations placed on Filipino teachers are substantial, as they are entrusted with the crucial task of nurturing young minds, fostering positive attitudes, and shaping the next generation's character. This is embedded in the "Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers" and the "Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers," which exemplify the commitment to maintaining high standards in teaching. These documents underscore the significance of teacher conduct, competence, and character, creating an implicit expectation of emotional regulation within the profession.

Educational reforms and strategies have been carried out with respect to emotional regulation among teachers in the Philippine

educational context (Bonior, 2019). In terms of strategy, Go et al. (2020) press for teachers' problem compartmentalization as one of the aspects that need to be targeted among Filipino teachers, especially as they deal with personal problems yet are still expected to display desirable dispositions in the school. In terms of intervention programs, the Department of Education through Department Order No. 14, series of 2020 attempts to address emotional welfare through the provision of mental health and psycho social support services to only of the students but also teachers and personnel.

But while these strategies and intervention programs are concerned with teachers' mental health and emotional well-being, the researcher has not found any published study in the local literature that is dedicated towards addressing how Filipino private school teachers regulate their emotions and manage frustration within their school environments.

A teacher is a professional who is responsible for assisting students in acquiring knowledge, skill, and virtue. Moreover, just like other people or professions, teachers have emotions and feelings experienced in their work environment. Since students and teachers can express a wide range of emotions, emotions naturally play a crucial role in the classroom. There are many moments in the classroom where both good and negative emotions might easily arise (Tyng et al., 2017). In addition, it is recognized that the classroom is a significant source of emotion and emotional exhaustion for teachers. Controlling negative emotions is crucial for preserving discipline, fostering relationships, projecting one's professional identity, and maintaining one's mental health (Morris & King, 2018).

Moreover, significant factors that influence teacher moods in the classroom are interpersonal interactions with students and classroom management. More specifically, connections between students and teachers have both interpersonal and professional components (Hagenauer et al., 2015). The interpersonal or emotional dimension is conceived as closeness, which indicates the association between the teacher and the student such as warmth, trust, affection, and openness, among other things, which reflects struggles and unfavorable perceptions (Pianta, 2001). Teachers frequently experience emotions as a result of interpersonal components of teacher-student relationships (Hargreaves, 2000) of both positive valences (e.g., joy, excitement, warmth, and affection) and negative valences (e.g., anger, frustration, and anxiety; Jiang et al., 2016).

However, regarding teacher-student conflict, it has been suggested that instructors' issues with regulating emotions and their previous analyses in the face of challenging student conduct are factors in teacher burnout (Chang, 2009). For example, when disruptive classroom events occur, unpleasant emotions (i.e., anger and frustration) can lead to burnout for teachers who are unable to regulate their emotions (Durr et al., 2014).

Furthermore, emotions play a significant role in classroom life and are frequently seen in interactions between teachers and students (Hosotani & Imai-Matsumura, 2011). Humans have long heavily relied on their emotions to get through each day. It has an impact on their actions as well as how they perceive their surroundings. Although many believe that emotions are not always a crucial aspect of their lives, it has been scientifically demonstrated that emotions profoundly impact them, often without their awareness. Since students and teachers can express a wide range of emotions, emotions naturally play a crucial role in the classroom.

As a fact, to interact with their social environment effectively, people must have the ability to regulate their emotions, both their own and those of others. Emotion regulation refers to a person's capacity to manage emotional reaction. Due to the dynamic nature of human emotional reactivity and its pervasive influence in all circumstances, abilities are essential for daily functioning. Basic physiological mechanisms that modulate arousal serve as the basis for emotional regulation abilities. Understanding the role of social and emotional processes in adaptive emotion regulation may help in developing effective preventative intervention programs (Dollar & Calkins, 2020).

In line with this, emotion regulation is the capacity to exert control over one's emotional state. It could entail evaluating a stressful situation to lessen anger or anxiety, covering up obvious signs of fear or grief, or concentrating on things that make someone joyful or peaceful (Psychology Today). Educators develop various techniques to regulate their emotions in the classroom, such as altering an emotion's valence, intensity, or time course. As a result, the important matter is what teachers do with it when they get frustrated with how to handle it. They are teachers, so their first step should be to respond positively to the student and try to understand them. They should only react after understanding the cause of our frustration. They must be good motivators and motivate their students too. If the student's behavior is the cause of our frustration, then they should try to understand the root cause of the problem. An important facet of teachers' competence is their ability to adaptively regulate their emotions in the classroom. As a result, teachers' emotional displays in front of students might not reflect their actual emotional experiences. The emotions are connected to important teacher outcomes like instruction quality and teacher well-being (Chen, 2018). Teachers must manage their emotions to respond to emotional classroom settings and perform successfully. As a result, while in the classroom, both teachers and students feel and express a wide range of emotions. The teacher is frequently in charge of establishing and guiding the emotional atmosphere in the classroom. Teachers may want to control their own emotions or the emotions of their students in order to create the best emotional atmosphere.

Meanwhile, frustration is a negative emotion that teachers often experience. It is a complicated emotion that often stems from feelings like disappointment, fear, and stress (Mental Health America, n.d.). Because everyone has a unique coping style with negative emotions like these, they can materialize and be expressed in various ways. The physiological component precisely demonstrates how bad emotions might appear in the classroom. The most noticeable alteration also includes facial expressions.

Moreover, there are instances when teachers get frustrated because the students are talking to each other. During the discussions, it is

necessary to maintain silence while the teacher is talking because once ears catch even a single sound, the culprit will answer that teachers do not want to have their discussions in a noisy environment. If the students talk to one another, they are not interested in listening to the discussion. This disciplinary action must be implemented since talking to one another during a teacher's discussion insults the part of the teacher who is trying very hard. Teachers also become angry when they believe students' poor academic work is due to controllable factors, such as laziness or inattention (Helpline PH, 2020).

In addition, frustration is just part of the experience of teaching in sometimes uncontrollable situations. They do not have much control, and feeling out of control can lead to frustration. A number of people might be drawn to a profession like teaching in the first place because they are kind, caring, and are more nurturing, which may be associated with a tendency to lose their temper. A teacher frustrated by the misbehavior and violation of rules of the students, factors outside the classroom that make it difficult to teach well, uncooperative colleagues, and parents who do not follow appropriate behavior norms or are perceived as uncaring and irresponsible. Many teachers report that most experiences of frustration are not minor, momentary feelings but intense, last more than an hour, and are associated with noticeable bodily sensations (IH World, 2021). Therefore, teachers must learn to deal with their emotions to respond to and perform well in emotionally charged classroom circumstances.

As a result, it has been discovered that negative emotions like frustration, which teachers regularly report experiencing, lower teachers' intrinsic motivation and raise students' negative emotional experiences. There is much information on the negative effects of teachers' negative emotions on their well-being and students' academic success. In general, instructors' emotions are important components of education. Some argue that a new direction in emotional research is to investigate how teachers' emotions, particularly negative emotions, could be regulated. Researchers are still studying teachers' ability to control their emotions. Ineffective teaching and classroom management, burnout, emotional weariness, and teacher attrition have all been linked to a lack of understanding of how teachers regulate their emotions. In this context, there is an urgent need for research into how instructors manage their emotions (Macdonald, 1999; Olivier & Venter, 2003; Sutton & Wheatley, 2003; Chan, 2006; Carson & Templin, 2007; Sutton & Harper, 2009; Fried, 2011, as cited in Jian et al., 2015).

However, the difficulties with emotion regulation play a fundamental role in our experiences as humans, shaping attitudes, actions, and social interactions. Nevertheless, negotiating the emotional landscape can be difficult at times. The fact that emotions are complex and subjective is a big challenge. What one person interprets as joy may be sadness for another, highlighting the intrinsic diversity and complexity of emotional states. Emotions are also unpredictable and challenging to control since they can change quickly in reaction to both internal and external events. Societal and cultural conventions surrounding emotions can also hinder emotional expression and understanding. Some cultures may view some emotions as forbidden or inappropriate, which causes people to repress or reject their emotions. This can cause psychological distress and internal conflict. In addition, people may have trouble controlling their emotions, making it difficult to control the strength and duration of their emotional reactions. This problem may manifest itself as anything from persistent tension and anxiety to impulsivity and mood swings. Despite these obstacles, people can become more resilient and authentic in navigating the intricacies of their emotional lives by cultivating their emotional intelligence through self-awareness, empathy, and useful coping mechanisms.

Teachers can benefit greatly from this in a variety of spheres of their lives. Maintaining mental and emotional health depends on effective emotion regulation because it allows people to deal with the complexity of their emotions in healthy, adaptable ways. People who struggle with controlling their emotions face a variety of obstacles that can have a significant impact on their everyday functioning and overall quality of life. Among these difficulties is increased emotional reactivity, which increases a person's susceptibility to suffering severe and protracted emotional distress in reaction to stressors or triggers. Furthermore, maladaptive coping mechanisms such as avoidance or rumination may result from difficulty regulating emotions. These behaviors can intensify negative feelings and hinder the ability to solve problems effectively. Moreover, chronic emotional dysregulation frequently links to an increased risk of developing mood disorders, including depression and anxiety, as it impedes the ability to feel happy emotions and contributes to persistent negative affect. Emotional regulation issues can impact interpersonal relationships in addition to an individual's well-being. People with dysregulation may find it difficult to communicate their feelings in a healthy way or to relate to others' experiences, which can result in disagreements and social distancing. Additionally, poor emotion regulation can decrease cognitive abilities such as memory, concentration, and decision-making, which might worsen emotional distress and negatively impact adaptive functioning in general. In general, treating issues related to emotion regulation is essential to improving people's mental and emotional well-being, boosting their capacity to handle life's obstacles, and establishing relationships that are beneficial.

Difficulties in emotion regulation, or the strategies that people employ to control their feelings (Gross, 2015), can have a big influence on how people react to frustration. When faced with challenges or frustrations, people who have trouble controlling their emotions frequently turn to unhealthy coping techniques (Aldao et al., 2010). This can involve actions that aggravate rather than lessen frustration, such as avoidance, aggressiveness, or self-blame (Gross & Thompson, 2007). Moreover, those who struggle to control their emotions may get frustrated more easily and for longer than people who can control their emotions well (Gratz & Roemer, 2004). Stress and interpersonal conflict may increase as a result of this elevated emotional reactivity (Troy et al., 2013). Furthermore, rumination and negative thought patterns might arise from challenges with emotion regulation, exacerbating feelings of frustration and adding to a powerless feeling (Nolen-Hoeksema et al., 2008). Moreover, poor emotional regulation can lead to a person's inability to solve problems since it prevents them from coming up with creative ways to get beyond challenges (Berkling & Znoj, 2008). Finally,

dissatisfaction can also have a negative effect on interpersonal interactions, especially if people express it in ways that are interpreted as unfriendly or counterproductive (DeSteno et al., 2013). All things considered, mastering the art of healthy emotion regulation is essential to controlling frustration and resolving difficult circumstances with flexibility and resilience.

This study is supported by two theories: Process Model of Emotion Regulation and Appraisal Theory. The first theory proposes that people's emotions constitute simply responses to the outside world, and it will serve as the foundation for controlling people's emotions while the second theory describes the mental procedure by which individuals assess essential factors to their well-being and trigger feelings that stimulate the body for action.

More so, the relationship between emotional regulation, frustration and difficulties in emotion regulation in the context of teachers' experiences remains understudied and has not been clearly established in the local literature.

This study was helpful to teachers, especially those who have struggled with issues that have left them feeling frustrated in their daily lives, especially in terms of Teaching. The findings might teach individuals how to control their emotions and enhance their teaching abilities despite feeling such negative emotions. The study was beneficial for teachers to employ effective teaching strategies to facilitate a holistic approach to students' emotional development. For the students, the study may acknowledge the boundaries with their teachers and demonstrate discipline and how to organize themselves for their acts or behavior. The administrator can benefit from this study as the results of this study can be used for future development programs to provide significant knowledge about and Difficulties in emotion regulation. Also, they can hold teachers' development programs to help plan and utilize effective teaching strategies and assessments to ensure quality education.

Finally, the study's findings would benefit future researchers in the field of Teaching and other related fields. This study would be used for further related research since this is the only local research conducted in a similar survey.

Research Questions

This study aims to measure the emotion regulation, frustration and difficulties in emotion regulation of selected private colleges' teachers. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. civil status and
 - 1.4. years of service?
2. What is the respondents' level of emotion regulation using Roth's (2009) Emotion Regulation Inventory Scale in terms of:
 - 2.1. integration;
 - 2.2. suppression and
 - 2.3. dysregulation?
3. What is the respondents' level of difficulties in emotion regulation using Gratz, K. L., & Roemer, L. (2004) Difficulties in Emotion Regulation Scale (DERS)?
4. What is the respondents' level of frustration using Harrington's (2005) Frustration Discomfort Scale?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' level of emotion regulation, frustration and difficulties in emotion regulation?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' profile on level of emotion regulation, frustration and difficulties in emotion regulation?
7. Based from the findings of the study, what action plan can be proposed?

Methodology

Research Design

The present study utilized a quantitative correlational research design that entails measurement and presupposes that it can quantify the phenomenon under investigation. It intends to analyze data for patterns and correlations and validate the measurements produced (Watson, 2015). It investigates correlations between variables without requiring the researcher to control or manipulate them and represents the intensity and direction of the relationship, which will have either a positive or negative direction (Bhandari, 2021). The data needed was obtained from a google form which provides a quantitative description of a population's attitudes or opinions by generalizing from a sample (Creswell, 2014). By describing the current situation or phenomenon, this research design allowed the researcher to present the demographic profile of the respondents and the level of emotion regulation, frustration and difficulties in emotion regulation among private college teachers. This research design allowed the researcher to assess whether the respondents' profile such as their age, sex, civil status, and years of service has a significant relationship between emotion regulation, frustration and difficulties in emotion regulation. Also, it was assessed whether or not there is a significant relationship between emotion regulation, frustration and difficulties in emotion regulation among private college teachers.

Participants

The study's participants were private teachers at selected private colleges. The researcher utilized the stratified random sampling technique, as this is the most appropriate method to obtain the respondents for the study. It is a technique in which researchers split a population into smaller subgroups, or strata, based on shared members' features and then randomly choose from these subgroups to generate the final sample (Simkus, 2022). The researcher chose two private schools, namely Lipa City Colleges and the College of Science, Technology, and Communication, Inc. (CSTC), which are convenient to access. Raosoft calculated the representative sample from the total population of teachers ($N = 138$). With a margin of error of 0.05, a confidence level of 0.95, and a response distribution of 0.50, the researcher needs to recruit 102 teachers among the two selected schools. However, the researcher plans to send the survey to at least 90 respondents, accounting for potential anomalies, withdrawals, or invalid responses.

Instrument

A demographic data form containing their age, sex, status, and years of service was completed by the respondents to the study.

To assess emotion regulation, it was measured using the Emotion Regulation Inventory Scale consisting of 18 items developed by Roth et al., (2009) to assess the regulation of negative emotions. This questionnaire has three subscales: Integration, Suppression, and Dysregulation. This scale is used by the study of Roth et al. (2009), which determined that Cronbach's alpha was 0.79 in Integration, 0.80 in Suppression, and 0.86 in Dysregulation, indicating high reliability. It was rated on a 5-point Likert scale, with 1 indicating "Completely disagree," and 7 indicating "Completely agree." The verbal interpretation of this 7-point Likert Scale is Very Low in 1 (Completely disagree) with a mean value of 1.00-1.79; Low in 2 (Disagree) with a value of 1.80-2.59, Moderately Low in 3 (Neutral) with a mean value of 2.60-3.39; Average in 4 (Agree) with a mean value of 3.40-4.19; Moderately High in 5 (Completely agree) with a mean value of 4.20-5.00.

To assess the emotion regulation difficulties was measured using the emotional regulation difficulties scale (DERS) (Gratz & Roemer, 2004). The scale is designed to be a self-report measure consisting of six domains: Nonacceptance of Emotional Responses (NONACCEPT), Difficulties Engaging in Goal-Directed (GOALS), Impulse Control Difficulties (IMPULSE), Lack of Emotional Awareness (AWARE), Limited Access to Emotion Regulation Strategies (STRATEGIES), and Lack of Emotional Clarity (CLARITY). Each subscale has items describing various behavior. It was rated using a 5-point Likert scale, from 1 (Almost never) to 5 (Almost always). The scale's reliability was determined by calculating its internal consistency, which was 0.95, using the Alpha Cronbach formula. The scale has a high degree of internal validity because all items correlate with a score greater than 0.30.

To assess the frustration, it was measured using the 28 items of the Frustration Discomfort Scale developed by Harrington (2005). This scale is divided into four subscales: discomfort intolerance, emotional intolerance, achievement frustration, and entitlement. The Cronbach's alpha of the respective subscale was .88, .85, .87, and .84. It was rated on a 5-point Likert scale, with 1 indicating "Absent" and 5 indicating "Very Strong." The verbal interpretation of this 5-point Likert Scale is Very Low in 1 (Absent) with a mean value of 1.00-1.79; Low in 2 (Mild) with a mean value of 1.80-2.59; Moderate in 3 (Moderate) with a mean value of 2.60-3.39; High in 4 (Strong) with a mean value of 3.40-4.19; and Very High in 5 (Very Strong) with a mean value of 4.20-5.00.

Procedure

The researcher will prepare the necessary documents, such as formal letters and informed consent, which was signed and approved by the research instructor. The letters accompanied by the research questionnaires was addressed to the Vice President for Administration, sent to the School of CSTC, Sariaya, Quezon, to the Director of Research and Development, and sent to the School of Lipa City Colleges, Lipa City. The researcher asked for their permission and approval to conduct the present study involving the teachers. Lastly, the researcher acquired permission from the research instructor to begin the data-gathering process. As for the questionnaires, they were encoded into Google Forms with an invitation letter and informed consent stating that respondents may either agree to participate or not. After receiving permission, the researcher works with the department's secretary or deans to help them disseminate the Google form links to the target respondents.

Data Analysis

To ensure the reliability of the analyses and interpretations of the gathered data from the questionnaires answered by the respondents, the researcher made use of the following statistical tools:

Frequency Count. This statistical tool was used in the table, which presented the actual distribution of the respondents' demographic profile in terms of their age, sex, civil status, years of service and school in frequency format.

Percentage. This was utilized to determine the relative position of the respondents profile.

Ranking. This was employed using the ordinal number of a value in the profile and assessment of the respondents on their level of emotion regulation, frustration and difficulties that was arranged in a specified order.

Weighted Mean. This was applied to know the average assessment of the respondents on their level of emotion regulation, frustration and difficulties. Pearson correlation coefficient. This tool was employed to determine the significant relationship between the

assessment of the respondents on their level of emotion regulation, frustration and difficulties; as well as the significant relationship between the profile variables and level of emotion regulation, frustration and difficulties.

Results and Discussion

This part of the study presents all the results of the data gathering procedures including their corresponding analysis, discussion, and interpretation as supported by existing literature and studies.

Profile of the Respondents.

The first problem of this study focuses on the profile of the faculty teachers in terms of their age, sex, civil status, school, and years of service.

Table 1. *Distribution of Profile of the Respondents*

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
20-23 years old	7	7.53	5
24-26 years old	21	22.58	2
27-29 years old	44	47.31	1
30- 33 years old	13	13.98	3
34 years old and above	8	8.60	4
Total	93	100	
Sex			
Female	48	51.61	1
Male	45	48.39	2
Total	93	100	
Civil Status			
Single	60	64.52	1
Married	33	35.48	2
Total	93	100	
Years of Service			
Less than a year	3	3.23	4
1 - 2 Years	8	8.60	3
3 - 4 Years	42	45.16	1
5 years and more	40	43.01	2
Total	93	100	
School			
Lipa City Colleges (LCC)	37	39.78	2
College of Science, Technology and Communication, Inc. (CSTC)	56	60.22	1
Total	93	100	

Table 1 shows the distribution of the demographic profile of the respondents.

When according to their age, 27-29 years old got the highest frequency, which was 44, a percentage of 47.31 at rank 1. The 20-23 year old got the least frequency of seven, a percentage of 7.53 at rank 5. The distribution of respondents across different age groups, as depicted in Table 1, highlights a clear concentration among individuals aged 24 to 29 years old, with the highest frequency and percentage. This demographic trend underscores a notable representation within the surveyed population, suggesting a potentially influential cohort within the study's findings and implications.

In terms of the demographic profile of the respondents according to their sex, the highest frequency was female, which got 48 of 51.61% of the total respondents at rank 1 while male got a frequency of 45, a percentage of 48.39% and a rank of 2. The data from the table revealed a significant predominance of female respondents. In contrast, male respondents constitute a much smaller proportion. Notably, there were no respondents classified as "Others" in terms of sex. This gender distribution within the sample population suggests a potential gender imbalance that may influence the interpretation and generalization of the study's findings.

With regard to the demographic profile of the respondents according to their civil status, the highest frequency was single which got 60 of 64.52% of the total respondents at rank 1 while married got a frequency of 33, a percentage of 35.48% and at rank 2. The analysis indicates that the majority of respondents were single. Additionally, a significant proportion of respondents were married individuals constitute a smaller portions. This distribution highlights the diversity of civil statuses within the sample population, which may have implications for understanding the study's findings in relation to relationship status.

The findings from the study on emotion regulation and frustration among selected college teachers reveal a notable trend in the years of service among the teacher-respondents. A significant majority, comprising 42 or 45.16% at rank 1 were in the service for 3 - 4 years while only three or 3.23% at rank 4 of the population, have accumulated more less than a year of experience in the teaching service. This suggests that a substantial portion of the teacher sample has garnered substantial tenure within the educational sector, potentially

indicating a wealth of practical knowledge, pedagogical expertise, and institutional familiarity. Furthermore, a smaller but still notable proportion of respondents, fall within the less than a year to 2 years bracket of teaching service, indicating a relatively newer cohort within the profession.

Finally, in terms of the demographic profile of the respondents according to their school, the highest frequency CSTC, which got 56 of 60.62% at rank 1 of the total respondents while LCC got a frequency of 37, a percentage of 39.38 and a rank of 2. The examination of the result revealed that the majority of respondents were affiliated with CSTC while a smaller proportion of respondents were associated with LCC. This distribution underscores the predominance of CSTC among the surveyed individuals, potentially reflecting the institution's significance within the context of the study's objectives and outcomes.

Level of Emotion Regulation of Selected College Teachers

The second problem of this study focuses on the assessment of the emotion regulation of selected college teachers in terms of Integration, Suppression, and Dysregulation and the findings are as follows.

In Terms of Integration

Table 2. *Level of Emotion Regulation in Terms of Integration*

	<i>Statements</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	In situations I feel stressed or anxious, it is important for me to try to understand why I feel that way	4.41	Completely Agree	1
2.	When I feel stressed or anxious, I usually try to understand the reasons	4.34	Completely Agree	2
3.	Sometimes, feelings of stress or anxiety help me to understand important things about myself	3.96	Agree	3
4.	There were occasions on which talking about my feelings of anxiety or stress helped me	3.42	Agree	6
5.	On occasions, feelings of anxiety or stress helped me to understand something about the situation I was in	3.69	Agree	5
6.	In situations in which I feel anxiety or stress, I try to understand what this indicates about me and my situation	3.78	Agree	4
<i>Weighted Mean</i>		3.94	Agree	

The disparity between the highest and lowest indicators of emotional regulation among selected college teachers sheds light on the nuanced ways in which educators perceive and manage their emotions within the context of their professional roles. The highest indicator, "In situations I feel stressed or anxious, it is important for me to try to understand why I feel that way," reflected a profound level of agreement on emotional insight and adaptive coping strategies among teachers, with a weighted mean of 4.41 categorizing that they completely agreed and high emotionally regulated. This suggests that while some educators recognize the potential insights offered by stress and anxiety, others may struggle to effectively understand and contextualize their emotional experiences. The lower score implies a tendency among some teachers to approach stressful situations reactively rather than proactively, perhaps indicating a lack of awareness or reluctance to engage in introspective reflection. Consequently, these educators may experience greater difficulty in managing their emotions and deriving constructive meaning from stressful circumstances, potentially leading to heightened levels of distress and reduced overall well-being.

On the other hand, the lowest indicator, "There were occasions on which talking about my feelings of anxiety or stress helped me" revealed that the respondents agreed on lower level of emotional regulation among college teachers, with a weighted mean of 3.42 and a rank of 6 categorizing them as moderately regulated. This suggests that many educators recognize the value of stress and anxiety as potential catalysts for personal growth and self-awareness, viewing them not merely as obstacles but as opportunities for introspection and learning. By embracing and learning from their emotional experiences, these teachers demonstrate a remarkable capacity to integrate their emotions constructively, harnessing them as tools for self-discovery and professional development.

The disparity between the highest and lowest indicators underscores the heterogeneity of emotional regulation strategies employed by college teachers and highlights opportunities for targeted interventions and professional development initiatives (Chang, 2020). Educators, who demonstrate high levels of emotional regulation, as evidenced by the highest indicator, could serve as valuable mentors and role models, sharing their insights and coping strategies with colleagues to promote a culture of emotional resilience and growth within the academic community (Tahereh, 2021). Conversely, teachers who exhibit lower levels of emotional regulation, as indicated by the lowest indicator, may benefit from targeted support and training programs aimed at enhancing their emotional awareness and coping skills (Esen, 2022). By addressing individual differences in emotional regulation and fostering a climate of support and collaboration, educational institutions can empower teachers to navigate the complexities of their profession with confidence and resilience, ultimately enhancing their effectiveness and well-being (Sakire, 2020).

The emotional regulation of selected college teachers, particularly in terms of integration, revealed a significant aspect of their professional demeanor and coping mechanisms. With a composite mean of 3.94, indicating a high agreement on the level of emotional regulation, these educators demonstrate a commendable ability to effectively manage and integrate their emotions within the context of their teaching roles. Integration, in this context, refers to the capacity to understand, accept, and express emotions in a constructive

and adaptive manner, both personally and professionally. This suggests that the surveyed teachers possess a strong sense of self-awareness and emotional intelligence, enabling them to navigate the complexities of the educational environment with resilience and composure.

High levels of emotional regulation among college teachers have profound implications for various facets of their professional practice. Firstly, it enhances their ability to foster positive and supportive classroom environments conducive to learning and student well-being. Teachers who are adept at integrating their emotions are better equipped to handle challenging situations, such as student conflicts or academic setbacks, with patience, empathy, and rationality. This, in turn, cultivates a sense of psychological safety and trust among students, facilitating deeper engagement and academic achievement. Moreover, the emotional regulation of college teachers plays a crucial role in their job satisfaction and overall well-being. Educators who exhibit high levels of emotional regulation are less susceptible to burnout and emotional exhaustion, as they possess effective coping mechanisms to manage the stressors inherent in the teaching profession. By maintaining a healthy balance between emotional engagement and detachment, these teachers can sustain their passion for teaching and maintain a sense of fulfillment in their work, despite encountering inevitable challenges and setbacks.

Furthermore, the integration of emotions among college teachers contributes to their professional growth and development. Through reflective practices and self-assessment, emotionally regulated educators can glean valuable insights from their emotional experiences in the classroom, refining their teaching strategies and interpersonal skills. By continuously adapting and refining their emotional regulation strategies, teachers can enhance their effectiveness in facilitating student learning and fostering positive teacher-student relationships. The high level of emotional regulation demonstrated by selected college teachers, particularly in terms of integration, underscores their resilience and adaptability in navigating the complex and demanding landscape of the teaching profession. By effectively managing their emotions, these educators create supportive learning environments, maintain their well-being, and foster their professional growth. As such, understanding and fostering emotional regulation among college teachers is essential for promoting positive outcomes in both educational settings and the broader society.

In Terms of Suppression

Table 3. *Level of Emotion Regulation in Terms of Suppression*

	Statements	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1.	I almost always try not to express my stress or anxiety	4.03	Agree	4
2.	When I feel stressed or anxious I almost always conceal it, so others will not notice	4.12	Agree	1
3.	I try to ignore feelings of stress or anxiety	3.77	Agree	2
4.	In any situation, I prefer not to express my stress or anxiety	3.93	Agree	5
5.	I do not show my stress or anxiety to others	3.89	Agree	6
6.	I try not to refer to the feelings of stress or anxiety I sense in myself	3.90	Agree	3
	Weighted Mean	3.94	Agree	

The variation between the highest and lowest statement indicators of emotional regulation among selected college teachers, particularly in terms of suppression, illuminates the nuanced ways in which educators manage their emotional expressions within professional contexts. The highest statement indicator, "When I feel stressed or anxious I almost always conceal it, so others will not notice," with a mean of 4.12, a rank of 1 and agreed them as emotionally regulated that reflected a prevalent tendency among teachers to consciously regulate their outward displays of stress or anxiety. This suggests that many educators prioritize maintaining a composed and professional demeanor in the presence of others, potentially to avoid burdening colleagues or students with their emotional struggles. By concealing their stress or anxiety, these teachers demonstrate a capacity for self-control and adaptability, contributing to a harmonious and supportive atmosphere within educational settings.

On the contrary, the lowest statement indicator, "I do not show my stress or anxiety to others," with a mean of 3.89 and a rank of 6 also agreed as emotionally regulated, revealed a similar inclination among college teachers to suppress their emotional expressions, albeit to a slightly lesser extent. While still demonstrating a commitment to maintaining a composed exterior, teachers endorsing this statement may exhibit occasional lapses in emotional concealment or may adopt a more selective approach to suppressing their stress or anxiety. Despite the subtle differences in suppression strategies, both high-scoring indicators reflect a prevailing cultural norm within the teaching profession, wherein emotional restraint and professionalism are highly valued traits.

However, it is essential to consider the potential consequences of habitual suppression on the well-being of college teachers. While the ability to conceal stress or anxiety may enable educators to navigate challenging situations with poise and professionalism, prolonged or excessive suppression can have detrimental effects on mental health and job satisfaction. Teachers who consistently mask their emotional experiences may experience heightened levels of emotional dissonance and psychological strain, leading to burnout, decreased job performance, and strained interpersonal relationships. Moreover, the persistent effort to maintain a facade of emotional composure may impede authentic communication and hinder opportunities for mutual support and collaboration within academic communities.

While the high levels of emotional regulation demonstrated by selected college teachers in terms of suppression may reflect a commendable commitment to professionalism and self-control, it is essential to foster a culture of emotional authenticity and support

within educational settings (Wang, 2023). Encouraging teachers to cultivate self-awareness, seek appropriate outlets for emotional expression, and prioritize self-care can promote psychological well-being and resilience, ultimately enhancing their effectiveness and satisfaction in the teaching profession (Neubauer, 2021). By valuing emotional authenticity and promoting a holistic approach to educator well-being, educational institutions can create environments that nurture the personal and professional growth of teachers, benefiting both individuals and the broader academic community (Jamie, 2020).

Examining the emotional regulation of selected college teachers through the lens of suppression provides additional insight into their coping mechanisms and psychological well-being. Suppression involves the conscious effort to inhibit or conceal one's emotional expressions, often as a means of managing interpersonal interactions or conforming to social expectations. With a composite mean of 3.94, the respondents agreed that they were emotionally regulated in terms of suppression, these educators demonstrate a notable capacity to regulate their outward emotional displays in professional contexts.

High levels of suppression among college teachers suggest that they possess a degree of emotional self-control and adaptability in navigating the demands of their roles. By strategically regulating their emotional expressions, educators can maintain a sense of professionalism and authority in the classroom, effectively managing potential conflicts or disruptions while facilitating a conducive learning environment. This ability to modulate emotional responses may also contribute to the establishment of boundaries between personal and professional spheres, allowing teachers to compartmentalize their emotions and maintain a sense of equilibrium amidst the inherent challenges of their profession.

However, it is essential to consider the potential implications of excessive suppression on the psychological well-being of college teachers. While suppression may serve as a valuable coping mechanism in certain contexts, prolonged or habitual use of this strategy can have detrimental effects on mental health and interpersonal relationships. Teachers who consistently suppress their emotions may experience heightened levels of stress, anxiety, and emotional exhaustion, as the effort to conceal authentic feelings can lead to a sense of emotional dissonance and psychological strain. Moreover, excessive suppression may hinder genuine communication and rapport building with students and colleagues, potentially undermining the quality of teacher-student interactions and impeding collaborative endeavors within academic communities.

Thus, while high levels of suppression among selected college teachers may reflect a commendable degree of emotional regulation and adaptability in professional settings, it is crucial to promote a balanced approach to emotion management that acknowledges the importance of authenticity and self-expression. Encouraging teachers to cultivate self-awareness and emotional literacy can empower them to navigate the complexities of their profession with greater resilience and authenticity, fostering environments of trust, empathy, and mutual support within educational settings. By promoting a culture of emotional intelligence and well-being, educational institutions can empower teachers to thrive personally and professionally, ultimately enhancing the quality of teaching and learning experiences for all stakeholders involved.

In Terms of Dysregulation.

Table 4. *Level of Emotion Regulation in Terms of Dysregulation*

	<i>Statements</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Verbal Interpretation</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.	It's difficult for me to control my anxiety or stress and they turn up in ways I don't like	2.74	Neutral	6
2.	When I am stressed or anxious, generally I feel I have little control over my behavior	3.47	Agree	1
3.	I often behave in a stressful or anxious way, even if I don't want to behave like that	3.21	Neutral	4
4.	When I am anxious or stressed, I show my anxiousness even in situations which are not appropriate for it	3.03	Neutral	5
5.	My ability to function (perform) decreases significantly when I feel stressed or anxious	3.23	Neutral	3
6.	When I'm afraid or feel anxious I can't concentrate on other things I have to do	3.44	Agree	2
	Weighted Mean	3.19	Neutral	

The highest statement indicator, "When I am stressed or anxious, generally I feel I have little control over my behavior," with a mean of 3.42, a rank of 1, categorizing and agreed them as emotionally regulated, highlights a common perception among college teachers of feeling overwhelmed by stress or anxiety, potentially leading to a sense of loss of control over their actions. Despite the high level of emotional regulation overall, this indicator suggests that some educators may experience occasional lapses in self-control during times of heightened emotional arousal, reflecting the complex interplay between internal states and external stressors.

Conversely, the lowest statement indicator within the domain of dysregulation, "It's difficult for me to control my anxiety or stress and they turn up in ways I don't like," with a mean of 2.74, a rank of 6 and categorizing them as neutral and emotionally regulated, suggests a greater degree of self-awareness and proactive coping among college teachers. Despite experiencing difficulties in managing stress or anxiety, these educators demonstrate a willingness to acknowledge and address their emotional challenges, seeking out strategies to mitigate the impact of dysregulation on their well-being and professional functioning.

Examining the emotional dysregulation of selected college teachers provides insight into their ability to manage and modulate their emotional responses in the face of stress and anxiety. With a composite mean of 3.19 categorizing them as highly emotionally regulated, these educators demonstrate a commendable capacity to regulate their emotions effectively, maintaining a sense of control and composure even in challenging circumstances. However, within the domain of dysregulation, it is crucial to acknowledge the nuanced ways in which teachers experience and express their emotional distress.

The findings regarding emotional dysregulation among selected college teachers underscore the complexity of their emotional experiences and coping strategies within the teaching profession. While the majority of educators exhibit high levels of emotional regulation, there exists variability in their perceptions of control over their emotional responses and behaviors. By promoting self-awareness, resilience, and adaptive coping skills, educational institutions can support teachers in navigating the inevitable challenges and stressors of their profession, fostering a culture of emotional well-being and professional growth within academic communities.

The findings regarding emotional dysregulation among selected college teachers have several implications for both individual well-being and institutional support mechanisms. Firstly, recognizing the variability in teachers' perceptions of control over their emotional responses underscores the importance of personalized and targeted interventions aimed at enhancing emotional self-regulation skills. By providing educators with training and resources to identify and manage their stressors effectively, educational institutions can empower teachers to cultivate resilience and maintain optimal functioning in the face of adversity. Moreover, fostering a culture of openness and support regarding mental health and emotional well-being can reduce stigma surrounding emotional struggles and encourage educators to seek help when needed, ultimately promoting a healthier and more supportive work environment. Secondly, the high level of emotional regulation demonstrated by selected college teachers overall suggests a strong foundation for promoting positive teacher-student relationships and classroom dynamics. Teachers who are adept at managing their emotions are better equipped to create safe and supportive learning environments, where students feel valued, respected, and understood. By modeling healthy emotional regulation and interpersonal skills, educators can foster a sense of trust and connection with their students, enhancing engagement, motivation, and academic achievement. Thus, investing in strategies to promote emotional intelligence and empathy among teachers can have far-reaching benefits for student well-being and educational outcomes.

Addressing emotional dysregulation among college teachers requires a multifaceted approach that integrates individual self-care practices with systemic support mechanisms (Donker, 2020). Educational institutions can implement initiatives such as mindfulness training, stress management workshops, and counseling services to provide teachers with the tools and resources needed to navigate the emotional demands of their profession effectively (Wang Y. , 2022). Additionally, fostering a culture of collegiality and peer support can create opportunities for educators to share experiences, strategies, and coping mechanisms, reducing feelings of isolation and enhancing overall resilience. By prioritizing the emotional well-being of teachers, educational institutions can cultivate a healthier and more sustainable teaching workforce, ultimately benefiting both educators and students alike (Greenier, 2021).

Level of Difficulties in Emotion Regulation of Selected College Teachers

The highest statement indicator, "When I'm upset, I have difficulty getting work done," with a weighted mean of 4.00 and a rank of 1 indicating their difficulty most of the time, suggests that many teachers struggle to maintain productivity and focus during periods of emotional distress. This difficulty may stem from heightened emotional arousal, cognitive interference, or a lack of effective coping strategies, ultimately impeding their ability to fulfill job duties and responsibilities.

Conversely, the lowest statement indicator within the domain of difficulties in emotion regulation, "I care about what I am feeling," with a weighted mean of 2.18 at rank 36 also categorizing them as sometimes experiencing difficulty, highlights a potential disconnect between emotional awareness and effective regulation among college teachers. While educators may recognize and acknowledge their emotional experiences, they may still encounter challenges in effectively managing and responding to them in a constructive and adaptive manner. This discrepancy underscores the importance of promoting not only emotional awareness but also the development of practical emotion regulation skills that enable teachers to navigate the complexities of their profession with resilience and efficacy.

The examination of difficulties in emotion regulation among college teacher-respondents sheds light on the challenges they face in managing their emotional experiences within the context of their professional responsibilities. With a composite mean of 2.92 signified that they were experiencing about half the time of difficulty, these educators collectively report encountering significant obstacles in regulating their emotions effectively.

The prevalence of difficulties in emotion regulation among college teacher-respondents underscores the need for targeted interventions and support mechanisms to enhance their emotional well-being and job performance. Educational institutions can implement strategies such as mindfulness training, stress management workshops, and counseling services to provide teachers with the tools and resources needed to regulate their emotions effectively. By fostering a culture of emotional intelligence and resilience, institutions can empower teachers to navigate the inevitable challenges and stressors of their profession with confidence and competence, ultimately enhancing their job satisfaction, retention, and overall quality of teaching and learning. The findings regarding difficulties in emotion regulation among college teacher-respondents highlight the importance of integrating emotion regulation training and support into professional development programs within educational institutions. By providing teachers with opportunities to enhance their emotional awareness and develop practical coping strategies, institutions can empower educators to navigate the emotional demands of their profession more

effectively. Training initiatives focused on emotion regulation skills, such as mindfulness, cognitive reappraisal, and stress management techniques, can equip teachers with the tools and resources needed to regulate their emotions adaptively, ultimately enhancing their well-being and job performance.

Table 5. *Level of Difficulties in Emotion Regulation*

<i>Statement Indicators</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>R</i>
1. I am clear about my feeling	3.87	MT	3
2. I pay attention to how I feel	3.99	MT	2
3. I experience my emotions as overwhelming and out of control	2.51	S	29
4. I have no idea how I am feeling	2.18	S	36
5. I have difficulty making sense out of my feelings	2.32	S	34
6. I am attentive to my feelings	2.92	AHT	14
7. I know exactly how I am feeling	3.51	MT	5
8. I care about what I am feeling	3.28	AHT	8
9. I am confused about how I feel	2.69	AHT	24.5
10. When I'm upset, I acknowledge my emotions	3.79	MT	4
11. When I'm upset, I become angry with myself for feeling that way	2.67	AHT	26
12. When I'm upset, I become embarrassed for feeling that way	2.69	AHT	24.5
13. When I'm upset, I have difficulty getting work done	4.00	MT	1
14. When I'm upset, I become out of control	2.27	S	35
15. When I'm upset, I believe that I will remain that way for a long time	2.49	S	30
16. When I'm upset, I believe that I'll end up feeling very depressed	2.36	S	33
17. When I'm upset, I believe that my feelings are valid and important	3.27	AHT	9
18. When I'm upset, I have difficulty focusing on other things	3.34	AHT	6
19. When I'm upset, I feel out of control	2.41	S	31
20. When I'm upset, I can still get things done	2.88	AHT	17
21. When I'm upset, I feel ashamed with myself for feeling that way	2.73	AHT	22.5
22. When I'm upset, I know that I can find a way to eventually feel better	3.19	AHT	10
23. When I'm upset, I feel like I am weak	2.79	AHT	19
24. When I'm upset, I feel like I can remain in control of my behaviors	2.74	AHT	21
25. When I'm upset, I feel guilty for feeling that way	3.13	AHT	11
26. When I'm upset, I have difficulty concentrating	3.10	AHT	12
27. When I'm upset, I have difficulty controlling my behaviours	2.76	AHT	20
28. When I'm upset, I believe that there is nothing I can do to make myself feel better	2.57	S	28
29. When I'm upset, I become irritated with myself for feeling that way	2.73	AHT	22.5
30. When I'm upset, I start to feel very bad about myself	2.40	S	32
31. When I'm upset, I believe that wallowing in it is all I can do	2.87	AHT	18
32. When I'm upset, I lose control over my behaviours	2.91	AHT	15.5
33. When I'm upset, I have difficulty thinking about anything else	2.91	AHT	15.5
34. When I'm upset I take time to figure out what I'm really feeling	3.31	AHT	7
35. When I'm upset, it takes me a long time to feel better	2.64	AHT	27
36. When I'm upset, my emotions feel overwhelming	2.97	AHT	13
Weighted Mean	2.92	AHT	

Moreover, promoting a culture of empathy, understanding, and support within educational settings can create environments that validate and acknowledge the emotional experiences of teachers, reducing feelings of isolation and fostering a sense of belonging and camaraderie (Oktay, 2020). Educational leaders and administrators can play a crucial role in fostering a supportive organizational climate by prioritizing teacher well-being, actively listening to their concerns, and implementing policies and practices that promote work-life balance and psychological health (Hoffman, 2020). By prioritizing the emotional well-being of teachers, educational institutions can create environments that cultivate resilience, foster positive teacher-student relationships, and ultimately enhance the overall quality of teaching and learning experiences (Deng, 2022).

Furthermore, recognizing the interconnected nature of emotion regulation difficulties with other psychological variables, such as job satisfaction, burnout, and turnover intentions, underscores the importance of adopting a holistic approach to supporting teacher well-being (Braun, 2020). Educational institutions can implement comprehensive wellness initiatives that address the multifaceted needs of educators, including mental health resources, professional development opportunities, and organizational policies that promote a healthy work environment (Valente, 2022). Addressing the underlying factors contributing to emotion regulation difficulties and related outcomes, institutions can create cultures of care and support that empower teachers to thrive personally and professionally, benefiting both educators and students alike (Eyal, 2019).

Level of Frustrations of Selected College Teachers

The highest statement indicator, "I do not tolerate being taken for granted," with a weighted mean of 3.48 and a rank of 1 indicating their strong frustrations, and suggests that many teachers feel undervalued or unappreciated, potentially leading to feelings of

resentment and disillusionment. This sentiment underscores the importance of recognizing and valuing the contributions of teachers within educational institutions, fostering a culture of appreciation and respect that acknowledges their expertise, dedication, and hard work.

Table 6. *Level of Frustrations of Selected College Teachers*

<i>Statement Indicators</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>	<i>R</i>
1. I must have the easiest solution to problems; Not I tolerate having difficult moments	3.14	M	8.5
2. I hate having to wait for things that I would now	3.14	M	8.5
3. I have to get rid of disturbing sensations the as soon as possible; I can't stand them continuing	3.06	M	14.5
4. I can't stand being stopped from realizing my full potential	2.96	M	18
5. I can't stand doing tasks that look like too difficult	2.50	M	27.5
6. I can't stand other people taking action against my wishes	2.77	M	24.5
7. I can't stand feeling like I'm losing my mind	2.58	M	26
8. I can't handle the frustration of not reaching my goals	2.50	M	27.5
9. I can't stand working when I don't feel like it	2.79	M	23
10. I can't stand other people blocking what I want	2.84	M	21.5
11. I can't stand having certain thoughts	2.94	M	20
12. I don't tolerate lowering my standards too when it would be useful to do so	3.30	M	2
13. I hate having to force myself into homework	3.16	M	6.5
14. I do not tolerate being taken for granted	3.48	S	1
15. I can't stand situations in which I could feel myself upset/ annoyed/ agitated/ angry	3.08	M	13
16. I can't stand moving on from a job that I'm not completely satisfied	3.11	M	11
17. I can't stand the hassle of having to do things improvising	2.77	M	24.5
18. I hate having to give in to other people's demands people	3.16	M	6.5
19. I can't handle disturbing feelings	3.11	M	11
20. I can't stand doing a job if I'm not into it able to do it well	2.96	M	18
21. I can't stand doing things that involve a lot hassle	2.84	M	21.5
22. I hate having to change when they are the others to be wrong	3.28	M	3
23. I can't be happy with my life if things they do not change	3.06	M	14.5
24. I can't stand hearing that I'm not at my best of my potential	3.18	M	5
25. I hate having to persevere in tasks unpleasant	3.04	M	16
26. I don't tolerate criticism especially when I know about to be right	2.96	M	18
27. I can't stand losing control of mine emotions	3.27	M	4
28. I do not tolerate any failure in my self- discipline	3.11	M	11
Weighted Mean	3.00	M	

Conversely, the lowest statement indicator within the domain of frustration, "I can't stand doing tasks that look like too difficult," and "I can't handle the frustration of not reaching my goals" with an equal weighted means of 2.50, equal ranks of 27.5 categorizing them as mildly frustrated, suggests that while some tasks may present challenges, college teachers generally do not feel overwhelmed or disheartened by difficult or demanding assignments. This may reflect a sense of competence and confidence among educators in their ability to overcome obstacles and adapt to changing circumstances, mitigating the impact of frustration on their overall well-being and job satisfaction. However, it is essential to recognize that even low levels of frustration can accumulate over time and affect teacher morale and motivation if left unaddressed.

The findings regarding frustration among college teachers reveal significant insights into the challenges and stressors they encounter within the educational landscape. With a composite mean of 3.00 categorizing that they were frustrated about half the time, these educators collectively report experiencing a notable degree of frustration in their professional roles.

The prevalence of frustration among college teachers highlights the need for targeted interventions and support mechanisms to mitigate its negative impact on teacher well-being and job performance. Educational institutions can implement strategies such as professional development opportunities, mentorship programs, and workload management initiatives to address the underlying sources of frustration and enhance teacher resilience. By providing teachers with the tools, resources, and support they need to navigate challenges effectively, institutions can foster a culture of empowerment and engagement that promotes teacher retention and satisfaction. Moreover, fostering open communication channels and collaborative decision-making processes can empower teachers to voice their concerns and contribute to meaningful solutions that address the root causes of frustration within educational settings. By soliciting feedback from teachers and involving them in decision-making processes, institutions can cultivate a sense of ownership and investment in the school community, fostering a culture of trust, transparency, and accountability. Additionally, promoting a healthy work-life balance and prioritizing teacher well-being can help mitigate the effects of chronic stress and frustration, enhancing job satisfaction and overall quality of life for educators.

The findings regarding frustration among college teachers underscore the importance of recognizing and addressing the unique challenges and stressors they face within the educational landscape. By acknowledging the sources of frustration and implementing targeted interventions and support mechanisms, educational institutions can empower teachers to navigate challenges effectively, enhance job satisfaction and retention, and ultimately promote a culture of excellence and innovation in teaching and learning.

Furthermore, understanding the nuanced nature of frustration among college teachers can also inform the development of tailored support programs that address specific sources of dissatisfaction or discontent. For instance, if educators commonly express frustration related to administrative tasks or bureaucratic processes, institutions can streamline procedures, provide training on administrative tools, or designate support staff to assist with administrative responsibilities (Ruth, 2019). Similarly, if teachers report feeling frustrated by a lack of autonomy or input in decision-making processes, fostering a culture of shared governance and participatory leadership can empower educators to contribute their expertise and insights to organizational decisions (Ehsan, 2022). By proactively identifying and addressing the underlying factors contributing to frustration, educational institutions can create environments that promote teacher well-being, job satisfaction, and ultimately, student success. Moreover, exploring the relationship between frustration and other psychological variables, such as job satisfaction, burnout, and turnover intentions, can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the impact of frustration on teacher retention and organizational effectiveness (Bielak, 2020). Research suggests that high levels of frustration can contribute to feelings of burnout and dissatisfaction among educators, leading to decreased morale, productivity, and commitment to the profession. By examining the interplay between frustration and these related constructs, educational researchers and practitioners can identify potential intervention points and develop targeted strategies to mitigate the negative consequences of frustration on teacher well-being and organizational outcomes. By prioritizing the psychological health and professional fulfillment of college teachers, educational institutions can create environments that foster resilience, innovation, and excellence in teaching and learning (Li, 2022).

Relationship Between the Respondents' Level of Emotion Regulation, Difficulties and Frustrations

Table 7. *Relationship Between the Respondents' Level of Emotion Regulation, Difficulties, and Frustrations*

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Level of Emotion Regulations Versus Level of Frustrations:				
Integration	-0.29	0.00481	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Suppression	0.29	0.00481	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Dysregulation	0.12	0.25191	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Level Emotion Regulations Versus Level of Difficulties:				
Integration	-0.02	0.84909	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Suppression	-0.21	0.04335	Reject Ho	Significant
Dysregulation	0.34	0.00085	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Level of Frustrations Versus Level of Difficulties				
Frustration and Difficulties	0.32	0.00177	Reject Ho	Highly Significant

As stated in table 7, when the responses of the selected college teachers on their relationship between the level of emotion regulation through integration and the level of frustrations shows an r-value of -0.29 and have corresponding p-value of less than 0.01. Thus rejecting the hypothesis. This highly significant negative correlation suggests that individuals who effectively integrate their emotions experience lower levels of frustration. This finding aligns with existing literature, such as the study by Gross and John (2003), which demonstrated that adaptive emotion regulation strategies like cognitive reappraisal (a form of emotional integration) are linked to reduced negative emotions and enhanced psychological well-being.

On the other hand, the relationship between emotion regulation through suppression and the level of frustrations reveals an r-value of 0.29 and and have corresponding p-value of less than 0.01. Thus rejecting the hypothesis. This highly significant positive correlation indicates that individuals who suppress their emotions tend to experience higher levels of frustration. Suppression, as an emotion regulation strategy, has been found to be maladaptive, leading to increased negative emotions and psychological distress (Gross & Levenson, 1997).

The correlation between emotion dysregulation and frustration has an r-value of 0.12 and have corresponding p-value of more than 0.05, Thus failing to reject the hypothesis, indicating no significant relationship. This suggests that the inability to regulate emotions does not have a strong direct correlation with the level of frustrations experienced by the respondents.

The two most useful and widely applied emotion management techniques in daily life, according to emotion regulation process theory, are expressive suppression and cognitive reappraisal. The two have differing impacts on how emotion, thought, and social conduct are adjusted. According to Gross (1998)a, b, 1999, 2001), expression suppression is linked to unfavorable results while cognitive reappraisal is linked to favorable outcomes.

The early stages of emotions are when the cognitive reappraisal approach takes place. It is possible to lessen the reaction caused by emotional events by reevaluating and reinterpreting them. It can assist people in making wise judgments and successfully lessen unpleasant feelings and physical tension (Sheppes et al., 2011). (Heilman et al., 2010). Furthermore, it modifies the individual's interpretation of the significance of these events to influence social behaviors in a good way. It also has a strong correlation with wellness and mental health (Boden et al., 2012; Xu et al., 2020). It is an efficient method of suppressing unpleasant emotions that enhances life satisfaction (Gong et al., 2013).

After an emotion is experienced, the expression suppression method involves repressing and avoiding the emotion's expression. It is a

non-adaptive technique that does not lessen the psychological experience brought on by a bad feeling. Expression suppression technique users had comparatively more unpleasant experiences and less happy experiences, respectively (Wang and Guo, 2003), which lowers their mental health. According to Julian and Richard (2000), Gross (2002), Ohchner et al. (2002), Garnefski et al. (2004), expression suppression negatively affects other cognitive activities, affective experiences, and behaviors. It also necessitates the consumption of cognitive resources. Research has indicated that when it comes to preserving one's physical and mental well-being, cognitive reappraisal techniques outperform expression suppression (Gross and John, 2003; Moore et al., 2008; Hughes et al., 2011). The former can help people cope with life more effectively and lessen depressive symptoms to some extent (Garnefski and Kraaij, 2011).

According to Crumbaugh (1973) and Steger et al. (2009), the term "sense of life meaning" refers to an internal psychological experience in which individuals experience and comprehend the purpose of their lives in addition to realizing their objectives and missions.

When examining the relationship between emotion regulation and difficulties, the integration strategy shows an r -value of -0.02 and has a corresponding p -value of more than 0.05 , Thus failing to reject the hypothesis, indicating no significant correlation. Thus, effectively integrating emotions does not significantly relate to the level of difficulties encountered by individuals. However, emotion suppression shows a significant negative correlation with difficulties, with an r -value of -0.21 and has a corresponding p -value of less than 0.05 , Thus rejecting also the hypothesis, indicating that higher suppression is associated with fewer difficulties. This could be due to the short-term benefits of suppression in avoiding immediate emotional reactions, though long-term consequences are often negative (John & Gross, 2004).

Emotion dysregulation, however, has a highly significant positive correlation with difficulties, with an r -value of 0.34 and has a corresponding p -value of less than 0.01 . Thus rejecting the hypothesis, This suggests that individuals who struggle to regulate their emotions face more difficulties, supporting findings that emotional dysregulation is linked to various psychological problems and life challenges (Gratz & Roemer, 2004).

The perceived efficacy of a person's capacity to control negative affect is measured in this component of Gratz and Roemer's (2004) emotion regulation issues rather than the person's actual competence or techniques for controlling emotions. The theoretical justification for measuring a person's perceived capacity for emotional regulation stems from the belief that an individual's subjective assessment of their own abilities more fully explains the contextual dependence of emotion regulation strategies than does categorizing people's reported capacities as effective or adaptive in the lack of contextual knowledge (Gratz & Roemer, 2004).

Lastly, the correlation between frustration and difficulties is highly significant, with an r -value of 0.32 and has a corresponding p -value of less than 0.01 , Thus rejecting the hypothesis, indicating that higher levels of frustration are associated with greater difficulties. This aligns with research that frustration, as a negative emotional state, can exacerbate perceived challenges and hinder effective problem-solving (Aldwin, 2007).

A negative emotional state that develops when someone is unable to accomplish a goal; psychology has examined this state in great detail because of its significant influence on behavior and cognitive functions. Higher degrees of frustration are regularly linked to harder problems to solve and a more heightened sense of obstacles, according to research. The cognitive load theory, which holds that unpleasant emotions like frustration take up brain resources that could be used for efficient problem-solving, explains this association. Aldwin (2007) asserts that frustration intensifies perceived challenges, resulting in an increased awareness of barriers and impediments. This can lead to a vicious cycle in which the frustration itself becomes a major obstacle to solving the original issue. Moreover, frustration might reduce a person's cognitive flexibility, making it harder for them to think creatively or explore different options. For example, a study conducted in 2012 by Mark and Smith discovered that people who were highly frustrated were less likely to use adaptive problem-solving techniques and were more likely to use emotion-focused, less successful coping mechanisms. These results emphasize the crucial role that emotional control plays in problem-solving and imply that treatments targeted at lowering frustration may improve cognitive function and results under difficult circumstances.

Relationship Between the Respondents' Profile and their level of Emotion Regulations, Frustrations and Difficulties

As revealed in Table 8, when the responses of the selected college teachers on their level of emotion regulations were compared based on their ages, the computed r -value of 0.25 for dysregulation has a corresponding p -value of less than 0.05 , thus rejecting the hypothesis. On the contrary, the computed r -values of -0.09 for integration and -0.01 for suppression have corresponding p -values of more than 0.05 , thus failing to reject the hypothesis.

These implied that the responses of the selected college teachers on their level of emotion regulations has a direct significant relationship on dysregulation; and no indirect significant relationships on integration and suppression when compared based on their ages.

Studies have shown that older adults may exhibit different patterns of emotional regulation compared to younger adults, often involving greater acceptance of negative emotions and less use of suppression strategies (Gross, 1998; Charles & Carstensen, 2010). The positive correlation between age and dysregulation found in this study may reflect increased challenges in managing emotions as individuals age, possibly due to factors such as cumulative life stressors, changes in social roles, or physiological changes affecting emotional processing (Carstensen et al., 1999; Urry & Gross, 2010). while age appears to be associated with increased dysregulation among

college teachers in this study, no significant associations were found for integration and suppression. These findings underscore the complexity of emotion regulation across different stages of adulthood and highlight the need for further research to explore underlying mechanisms and potential interventions to support emotional well-being in educational settings.

Table 8. *Relationship Between the Respondents' Profile and their level of Emotion Regulations, Difficulties and Frustrations*

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Age				
Integration	-0.09	0.39093	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Suppression	-0.01	0.92421	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Dysregulation	0.25	0.01566	Reject Ho	Significant
Frustration	-0.13	0.21424	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Difficulties	0.08	0.44589	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Sex				
Integration	-0.06	0.56779	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Suppression	0.12	0.25191	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Dysregulation	-0.10	0.34023	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Frustration	0.12	0.25191	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Difficulties	-0.06	0.56779	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Civil Status				
Integration	-0.10	0.34023	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Suppression	0.10	0.34023	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Dysregulation	0.10	0.34023	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Frustration	-0.06	0.56779	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Difficulties	-0.06	0.56779	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Years of Service				
Integration	0.02	0.84909	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Suppression	0.21	0.04335	Reject Ho	Significant
Dysregulation	0.21	0.04335	Reject Ho	Significant
Frustration	-0.07	0.50494	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Difficulties	0.06	0.56779	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
School				
Integration	-0.29	0.00481	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Suppression	0.26	0.01184	Reject Ho	Significant
Dysregulation	-0.48	1.12E-6	Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Frustration	0.09	0.39093	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Difficulties	-0.42	0.00003	Reject Ho	Highly Significant

There are two perhaps distinct components that may apply to older persons when engaging in behavioral efforts to manage an emotional state (Isaacowitz & Blanchard-Fields, 2012). The first element, preference, deals with deciding the specific tactic to employ. Effectiveness or adaptability—the second factor—relates to how well the chosen technique controls the person's emotional state. According to Fung et al. (2019), older persons may differ and/or be more adept at regulating their emotions in terms of efficacy and/or preference.

The tactics used by older persons change from ineffective to efficient ones: It's possible for older folks to switch from the less successful emotion management techniques that younger adults tend to employ to more generally more successful ones. For instance, older persons may be better at regulating their emotions by switching to use comparatively more reappraisal and less suppression than younger adults, assuming reappraisal is generally more effective than suppression. In longitudinal data, people would add more effective tactics as they grew older and eliminate less successful ones; in cross-sectional data, this would show up as an age difference with older adults employing more effective methods.

When older persons apply strategies, they have a greater impact on emotional experiences than do people in other age groups. It's also plausible that the relative efficacy of the employed techniques contributes to age-related "better" emotion control. For instance, when both utilize attentional deployment—either naturally or when prompted to do so—older persons may profit from it more than younger adults. This may be the case because older persons apply the approach in a way that maximizes its affective benefits or because older adults' resources best accommodate the strategy. This could coincide with usage changes (older adults use it more and gain more from it) or not (both age groups use it to the same extent, but older individuals find it more useful).

Elderly people are more adept at matching tactics to what works in a given circumstance. One last possibility is that older adults might match strategies more closely to the needs of the specific context, which would be consistent with the everyday problem-solving literature that suggests older adults "tune" their problem-solving more closely to the nature of the problem than younger adults (Blanchard-Fields, 2007). Importantly, this cannot be demonstrated by research that only look at variations in the use of emotion control strategies, since using a variety of tactics can just indicate that some are ineffective or that people are just unsure of what to do and are trying everything. Rather, only a certain kind of variability in which techniques are tailored to specific settings indicates the flexibility

of emotion regulation (Aldao, 2013).

Crucially, each of these scenarios depends on the existence of age differences, either in mean levels or in correlations with other variables. While methods like equivalency tests and Bayesian analyses can support potentially meaningful null age effects (see Isaacowitz, 2020; Lakens et al., 2020), very few studies report equivalency tests. Studies that do not find significant age differences typically do not indicate age similarity.

Furthermore, when the responses of the selected college teachers on their level of emotion regulations were compared based on their years of services, the computed r -value of 0.21 for both suppression and dysregulation have corresponding p -values of less than 0.05, thus rejecting the hypothesis. Meanwhile, the computed r -value of 0.02 for integration has a corresponding p -value of more than 0.05, thus failing to reject the hypothesis.

These generalized that the responses of the selected college teachers on their level of emotion regulations have direct significant relationships in terms of suppression and dysregulation; and no direct significant relationship on integration when compared based on their years of services.

Integration involves effectively processing and managing emotions without suppressing or excessively amplifying them, reflecting a more adaptive approach to emotional regulation (Gross, 1998; Salovey & Mayer, 1990). This stability in integration strategies over time could indicate that educators maintain a consistent level of emotional competence or resilience, potentially through ongoing professional development, supportive work environments, or personal coping strategies (Gross & John, 2003; Grandey, 2000).

These findings contribute to our understanding of how occupational factors influence emotion regulation among educators and have implications for promoting emotional well-being in educational settings. They suggest that while tenure may influence certain aspects of emotional regulation (i.e., suppression and dysregulation), educators may retain stable and adaptive strategies (i.e., integration) throughout their careers, mechanisms underlying these relationships and identify effective interventions to support teachers in developing and maintaining healthy emotion regulation skills over time.

Diverse conceptualizations have been employed to depict the framework of people's psychological coping mechanisms for negative emotions. These models generally differentiate between two types of coping strategies: problem- and emotion-focused (Folkman and Lazarus, 1980, Folkman and Lazarus, 1985); engagement (active, approach) versus disengagement (avoidance, passive) (Roth and Cohen, 1986; Tobin et al., 1989); and primary (assimilative) versus secondary (accommodative) control coping (Weisz et al., 1984; for comprehensive reviews, see Skinner et al., 2003; Skinner and Zimmer-Gembeck, 2016). Problem-focused coping, such as planning strategies to achieve goals, involves attempting to resolve the issue by changing or removing the stressor, whereas emotion-focused coping, such as wishful thinking, aims to control upsetting feelings in the face of difficulty in order to lessen the psychological effects of stress. Similar to disengagement coping, which refers to attempts to mentally and physically remove oneself from the stressor and related emotions, engagement coping, such as support-seeking, comprises proactive attempts to deal with the stressful situation or related feelings.

Additionally, when the responses of the selected college teachers on their level of emotion regulations were compared based on their schools, the computed r -value of -0.29 for integration and -0.48 for dysregulation have corresponding p -values of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis. In addition, the computed r -value of 0.26 for suppression has a corresponding p -value of less than 0.05, thus rejecting the hypothesis.

These inferred that the responses of the selected college teachers on their level of emotion regulations have high indirect significant relationships in terms of integration and dysregulation; and direct significant relationship on suppression when compared based on their schools.

These results can be understood According to Gross (1998), emotion regulation involves processes by which individuals influence which emotions they have, when they have them, and how they experience and express these emotions. Schools with supportive and collaborative environments may help teachers better integrate their emotions, reducing dysregulation. In contrast, schools with high demands and low support might increase emotional dysregulation among teachers. Hargreaves (2000) emphasizes that the emotional aspects of teaching are crucial, as emotions are deeply intertwined with teachers' professional identities and classroom practices.

Furthermore, Hochschild's (1983) concept of emotional labor suggests that teachers often need to manage their emotions to meet professional expectations. The direct relationship between suppression and schools may reflect how institutional norms and cultures dictate teachers' emotional expressions. For instance, in schools where emotional suppression is a norm, teachers might feel compelled to hide their true feelings to conform to professional standards. This can lead to increased emotional labor, impacting their well-being and job satisfaction.

The remaining profile variables such as sex were found no have direct significant relationships when compared to the level of emotional regulations in terms of suppression; and no indirect significant relationships in terms of integration and dysregulation as evidenced by the computed r -values with corresponding p -values of more than 0.05. Likewise, civil statuses were also found to have no direct significant relationships when compared to the level of emotional regulations in terms of suppression and dysregulation; and no indirect significant relationship in terms of integration as reported by the computed r -values with corresponding p -values of more than 0.05.

These therefore, failed to reject the hypothesis.

This outcome can be understood through the lens of existing literature. For example, research by Gross and John (2003) indicates that while there are individual differences in emotion regulation strategies, these differences are not strongly tied to demographic variables like sex. Instead, factors such as personality traits and contextual influences play a more significant role. This aligns with the current findings, where sex does not show a significant impact on teachers' emotional regulation

Similarly, civil status does not appear to influence emotion regulation significantly. This finding is supported by research from the field of occupational psychology. For instance, a study by Tuxford and Bradley (2015) suggests that workplace emotional experiences are more influenced by organizational culture and job-related stressors than by personal demographic factors. This indicates that teachers' emotional regulation strategies are likely shaped more by their professional environment and job demands than by their civil status.

Moreover, the absence of significant relationships between these demographic variables and emotion regulation underscores the complexity of emotional processes. According to Lazarus (1991), emotions are a result of an individual's appraisal of their environment, which involves cognitive processes that transcend simple demographic categorizations. This perspective suggests that understanding teachers' emotional regulation requires a focus on the interaction between individual cognitive appraisals and the broader organizational context, rather than solely on demographic factors.

The study's findings that sex and civil status do not significantly impact emotion regulation among college teachers align with broader research. They highlight the importance of considering more nuanced and context-specific factors in understanding how teachers regulate their emotions, emphasizing the role of the professional environment and individual cognitive processes over demographic variables.

Displayed also in Table 8 were the responses of the selected college teachers on their level of frustrations when compared to their profiles. It were found out that no direct significant relationships on sex and school; and no indirect significant relationships on age, civil statuses and years of service as given by the computed *r*-values with corresponding *p*-values of more than 0.05, signifying the non-rejection of the hypothesis. According to Kyriacou (2001), teacher stress and frustration are influenced more by situational and contextual factors rather than demographic characteristics. Factors such as workload, student behavior, administrative support, and school policies tend to have a more direct impact on teachers' emotional states than personal demographics.

Moreover, studies by Klassen and Chiu (2010) found that while demographic variables like age and years of service may influence certain aspects of job satisfaction and stress, they do not uniformly predict levels of frustration. Instead, teachers' individual coping mechanisms, resilience, and perceptions of their work environment play a more critical role. This aligns with the current findings, where age, civil status, and years of service do not show significant relationships with frustration levels.

The absence of significant relationships between frustration and demographic variables suggests that frustration is a more universal experience among teachers, driven by job-related factors rather than personal profiles. For example, Maslach, Schaufeli, and Leiter (2001) emphasize that burnout, which includes frustration, is primarily a result of chronic workplace stress and is influenced by organizational factors rather than individual characteristics.

Furthermore, the lack of significant differences based on sex and school indicates that frustration is not confined to particular demographic groups or educational institutions but is a broader issue that can affect any teacher regardless of these factors. This finding is supported by research from Skaalvik and Skaalvik (2015), who found that teacher burnout and frustration are prevalent across different types of schools and among both male and female teachers.

Lastly, when the responses of the selected college teachers on their level of difficulties were compared to their schools, the computed *r*-value of -0.42 has a corresponding *p*-value of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis.

However, when the responses of the selected college teachers on their level of difficulties were compared to their ages and years, no direct significant relationships were found; as well as no indirect relationships existed on sexes and civil statuses as supported by the computed *r*-values with corresponding *p*-values of more than 0.05, yielding the non-rejection of the hypothesis.

The significant relationship between teachers' difficulties and their schools can be understood through the lens of organizational and environmental factors. According to Taris, Le Blanc, Schaufeli, and Schreurs (2005), school environments greatly influence teachers' experiences of job-related difficulties. Schools with supportive leadership, adequate resources, and positive climates tend to have teachers who report fewer difficulties. Conversely, schools with poor administrative support, high student misbehavior, and insufficient resources are associated with higher levels of teacher difficulties. The negative *r*-value (-0.42) suggests that as the quality of the school environment decreases, the level of difficulties faced by teachers increases.

In contrast, the absence of significant relationships between teachers' difficulties and demographic factors like age, years of service, sex, and civil status aligns with existing literature that suggests job-related difficulties are more closely tied to situational factors than personal characteristics. For instance, research by van der Doef and Maes (2002) indicates that while personal factors can influence stress perception, the actual sources of difficulties in the teaching profession are more often related to job demands and organizational conditions.

The findings also resonate with studies by Day and Gu (2009), who emphasize that teachers' professional lives and the challenges they face are shaped significantly by the context in which they work. While individual differences such as age and years of service can affect how teachers cope with difficulties, they do not necessarily determine the occurrence of these difficulties. The study's results suggest that systemic and environmental factors within schools play a more crucial role in influencing teachers' experiences of difficulties than demographic variables.

Conclusions

The following are the conclusions of this study.

The demographic profile of college teachers in the study reflects a diverse range of ages and experiences, with a notable concentration among individuals aged 27-29 years old and a majority having 3-4 years of teaching experience. This suggests that the surveyed population encompasses both early-career educators and those with substantial tenure, highlighting the importance of considering a variety of perspectives and experiences in understanding emotion regulation and frustration within the teaching profession.

The findings regarding emotion regulation indicate that college teachers exhibit high levels of emotional regulation, particularly in terms of integration and suppression. This suggests that educators possess a commendable ability to understand and manage their emotions constructively, contributing to a positive classroom environment and effective professional functioning. However, the presence of some difficulties in emotion regulation, such as dysregulation and challenges in managing emotional distress, underscores the need for targeted interventions to support teachers in navigating the complexities of their emotional experiences.

The reported levels of frustration among college teachers emphasize the importance of addressing factors contributing to feelings of being undervalued or unappreciated in their professional roles. While educators generally demonstrate resilience in navigating challenges, the prevalence of frustration underscores the need for institutions to foster cultures of appreciation and support that recognize the contributions of teachers and promote their well-being.

Difficulties in emotion regulation emerge as a significant concern among college teachers, highlighting the need for targeted interventions and support mechanisms to enhance their emotional well-being and job performance. Despite recognizing and acknowledging their emotional experiences, educators encounter obstacles in effectively managing and responding to them adaptively, underscoring the importance of promoting emotional awareness and developing practical emotion regulation skills within the teaching profession. Addressing these challenges can ultimately contribute to a more positive and supportive work environment for college teachers, benefiting both educators and students alike.

The following are the recommendations of this study.

Educational institutions should provide comprehensive emotional intelligence training programs designed specifically for college teachers. These programs can help educators develop practical strategies for recognizing, understanding, and effectively managing their emotions. Institutions can improve teachers' well-being, job satisfaction, and overall classroom effectiveness by providing them with the skills and resources they need to navigate the emotional demands of their profession.

Institutions should prioritize the development of supportive organizational climates that value and prioritize the well-being of college faculty. This can include putting in place policies and practices that promote work-life balance, offer opportunities for professional development and growth, and encourage open communication and collaboration among faculty members. Institutions can foster cultures of appreciation, respect, and support, allowing teachers to feel valued, motivated, and empowered to thrive both personally and professionally.

Recognizing the difficulties associated with emotion regulation and frustration, institutions should provide targeted interventions and support mechanisms to help college teachers manage their emotional experiences effectively. This can include providing counseling services, stress management workshops, and wellness programs tailored to educators' specific needs and concerns. Furthermore, mentorship programs and peer support networks can provide opportunities for teachers to share experiences, seek advice, and receive guidance from colleagues, thereby improving their resilience and coping abilities.

Institutions should actively recognize and appreciate college teachers' contributions to the academic community. This may include celebrating accomplishments, recognizing milestones, and expressing gratitude for their dedication and commitment to student success. Institutions that promote a culture of appreciation and recognition can reinforce the value of teachers' work, boost morale and job satisfaction, and foster a sense of belonging and connection within the educational community.

Teachers should implement effective time management strategies. Prioritizing tasks by creating a detailed to-do list and focusing on high-priority items first can significantly reduce the stress associated with last-minute preparations. Setting clear boundaries between work and personal time ensures that teachers allocate specific periods for planning, grading, and relaxation, preventing burnout. Additionally, delegating tasks and collaborating with colleagues can ease the workload and provide mutual support, making the teaching experience more manageable and enjoyable.

Building positive relationships with students, colleagues, and parents fosters a network of respect and understanding, offering both

emotional and professional support. Creating a positive atmosphere in the classroom through effective management techniques, such as positive reinforcement, clear expectations, and consistent routines, can enhance student engagement and reduce behavioral issues. Furthermore, teachers should prioritize self-care by engaging in activities that promote well-being, such as exercise, hobbies, and relaxation techniques. Pursuing professional development opportunities can also rejuvenate teachers, equipping them with new strategies and ideas to keep their teaching practice fresh and motivating. By focusing on these areas, teachers can create a more fulfilling and less frustrating teaching experience.

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